

TRANSLATION TRANSFORMATION AS ONE OF THE WAYS TO ACHIEVE ADEQUACY IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS

Ismoilova Marxabo Abduraximovna

ESP teacher of

Bukhara State Medical Institute

named after Abu Ali Ibn Sina

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8008510>

It is very important for a translator to know the "precedents" of translation - the most typical, proven translation solutions. V.N. As Komissarov noted, the translator's knowledge of rules, styles and stereotypes helps to quickly find a translation option under time constraints.

Key words: transformation, equivalence, generalization, contextualization, omission, syntactic transformation

Translation transformation is translation methods that consist in replacing regular correspondences with irregular (contextual) ones, as well as the linguistic expressions themselves resulting from the use of such methods.

The use of transformations as a technique should be motivated by the fact that they provide greater equivalence than any possible regular adaptations, avoiding the negative consequences of using regular games in certain contexts.

According to A.F. Arkhipov, the reasons for using transformations can be:

- desire to avoid literalism;
- the desire to idiomatize the translation, bring it closer to the norms of the translation language;
- the need to eliminate interlinguistic differences in the design of the same members of the sentence;
- the desire to avoid word formation models in a foreign translated language;
- desire to avoid unnaturalness, non-aesthetic, uncomfortable, incomprehensible and illogical translation;
- striving for a more concise version of the translation (if possible); this compression of the translated text compensates for its inevitable increase in other segments.

Classifications of translation transformations

There is no universal classification of translational changes: existing classifications are characterized by the breadth or relative narrowness of the approach. A translator can take one of them as a basis and creatively revise and supplement it in the future.

Transformation is the basis of many translation methods. L. S. Barkhudarov understands the term "transformation" as a certain relationship between two linguistic or speech units, one of which is original, the other is created on the basis of the first, and under the term translation conversions there are many and qualitatively different . interlinguistic transformations that are carried out to achieve translation equivalence ("translation adequacy") despite the differences in the formal and semantic systems of the two languages.

There are two main groups of transformations: grammatical and lexical. Let's consider the types of lexical transformations. In "Translation Course" Latishev L.K. defines lexical

transformations as "deviations from dictionary correspondences". In the lexical systems of the English and Russian languages, there are inconsistencies that manifest themselves in the type of semantic structure of the word.

The essence of lexical transformations is that "the translation of the source language consists in replacing individual lexical units (words and phrases) in the source language with lexical units that are not equivalent in the dictionary of the translation language and have a different meaning than the units they translate."

Z. E. Roganova defines the structural and semantic methods of achieving adequacy. In the first case, this is the rejection of the original form, the transfer of individual words from one sentence to another, changing the order of sentences, their syntactic patterns, separating and combining sentences. Semantic changes include adequate replacement, concretization, generalization, method of logical development of the concept, compensation, antonymic translation, insertion and removal of words, replacement of one part of speech with another.

American linguist J. Nida in his book "To the Science of Translation" provides information about translation modifications, including addition of suffixes, omission of suffixes, and changes. The section "Adding extras" describes the following cases:

- 1) filling in ellipses;
- 2) forced explanation due to the ambiguity of the original or the desire to avoid false associations;
- 3) suffix when changing the grammatical structure (showing the actor when changing the voice);
- 4) clear transmission of hidden meaning;
- 5) answers to rhetorical questions;
- b) use of classifiers (for example, "in the city of Bochum" as a translation of the phrase "in the city of Bochum");
- 7) repeating a part of the previous sentence as a reference;
- 8) use of lexical doublets.

Among the existing classifications, first of all, it is worth noting the classification of L. S. Barkhudarov, who reduced the transformation to 4 main types of changes:

1. Changing the order of words in a sentence ("perestanovki");
2. Parts of speech, words with a general meaning, words with a more specific meaning, antonymic substitutions, substitutions ("zameny");
3. Use of lexical additions as compensation for the loss of grammatical means of expressing certain meanings (dobavleniya);
4. Omitting certain words ("opushchenie")

Lexical transformations are often combined, so it is not always possible to clearly qualify them. In general, eight main types of lexical transformations can be distinguished: concretization, generalization, lexical addition technique, omission technique, semantic development technique, antonymic translation technique, holistic transformation technique, compensation technique.

Concretization is the replacement of a word or phrase with a broad meaning in the source language by a word or phrase with a narrow meaning in the target language. As a rule, the vocabulary of the Russian language is more specific than the corresponding lexical units of the English language. This has been noted several times by linguists. Specification can be linguistic and contextual (speech). In linguistic concretization, the replacement of a word with

a broad meaning by a word with a narrow meaning is due to the differences in the structure of the two languages - the meaning as a transmitted unit in the source language, or differences in their stylistic features, or the requirements of grammatical order (the need to change the sentence syntactically, in particular, replacing a nominal predicate with a verb) or due to the lack of a lexical unit with the same broad meaning in the target language. Action verbs and speech verbs are concretized when translating into Russian.

The method of generalization is the opposite of concretization, because it consists in replacing the specific with a general concept, a specific concept with a general concept. When translating from English to Russian, it is used less often than concretization. This is due to the uniqueness of English vocabulary. The words of this language often have a more abstract character than the Russian words of the same concept.

The next subtype of lexical transformations is the lexical addition technique. The introduction of additional words is due to a number of reasons: differences in sentence structure and shorter English sentences require a more detailed expression of thought in Russian. The lack of a corresponding word or lexical-semantic variant of the given word also causes the introduction of additional words in the translation.

There is also a skipping technique. Omitting is the exact opposite of adding. When translating, words that are redundant due to their semantic content are often dropped. An example of redundancy is the use of "pair synonyms" common to all styles of English writing. This is not typical of the Russian language at all, so in such cases it is necessary to resort to omission when translating (that is, not to repeat a synonym - to replace two words with one word). Eliminating semantically redundant elements of the source text gives the translator the opportunity to perform the so-called "text compression", i.e. reduction of its total volume.

Adoption of semantic development consists in replacing vocabulary correspondences in translation with lexically related contextual ones. This includes metaphor and metonymy. If we consider that all important parts are divided into three categories: objects, processes and symbols, then to convey the same content through another language, the object can be replaced by its symbol, and the process by the object.

Often antonymic translation is used as a translation technique. This is replacing the concept expressed in the original with the opposite concept in the translation, reconstructing the entire statement accordingly in order to preserve the unchanged content plan. A special type of antonymic translation is the replacement of an adjective or adverb with an adjective (adverb) of a comparative or superlative degree in a positive degree or vice versa, and an affirmative construction with a negative one (or vice versa).

Holistic transformation is a type of semantic development. Adopting a complete transformation can be briefly defined as the transformation of a single word, and sometimes a whole sentence. In addition, the transformation is carried out holistically, not by elements.

Compensation in translation refers to replacing an intransitive element in the source language with other means that convey the same information, not necessarily in the same place as the original text. Compensation is always possible, especially when it is necessary to convey certain linguistic features of the original - dialectal coloring, irregularities, or purely internal linguistic meanings that describe individual features of speech, colloquialisms, words, etc. is used in non-existent cases.

Thus, the use of translation changes is primarily related to the transmission of the original content, the expression of the original idea. The translator should not try to preserve the

original in any case. Transformations are necessary to observe the "correctness" of language norms, and the translator's speech is accepted as "literate speech".

References:

1. Davlatova, M. H. (2019). Variability of Aspectual Meanings in English. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science*, 7(12.2019), 778-780.
2. Davlatova, M. H. (2020). An Integrative history of Aspectual meanings. *JournalNX*, 6(04), 17-22.
3. Davlatova, M. H. (2020). Aspectual variability of information culture in the history of the English language. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(3), 24-28.
4. Davlatova, M. H. (2020). Lexico-semantic Structure and Its Analysis on the Example of Verbs. *JournalNX*, 6(06), 189-192.
5. Davlatova, M. H. Relation of lexical-semantic structure of verbs in the linguistic essence. *IEJRD-International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(5).
6. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). SEMANTIC IMPLEMENTATION OF RESULTATIVE STRUCTURES. *METHODS*, 7(6).
7. Давлатова, М. Х. (2015). The role of songs in learning English. *Молодой ученый*, (10), 1145-1147.
8. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF RESULTATIVE STRUCTURES ACCORDING TO THEIR LINGUISTIC ESSENCE. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 2 (05), 475-479.
9. Давлатова, М. Х. (2017). Этапы работы с видеотекстами на занятиях Английского языка. *Интернаука*, (9-2), 16-19.
10. Давлатова, М. Х. (2015). The role of songs in learning English. *Молодой ученый*, (10), 1145-1147.
11. Melsovna, K. F., & Anvarovna, R. Z. (2023). THE LITERARY EMBODIMENT OF FLORA IN LAILA LALAMI'S BIOGRAPHICAL NOVEL "THE MOOR'S ACCOUNT". *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 82-90.
12. Melsovna, K. F., & Qizi, G. D. G. (2023). EUPHEMISM IN ORIGINAL AND TRANSLATION (IN THE EXAMPLE OF JACK LONDON'S NOVEL MARTIN EDEN). *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(04), 14-20.
13. Khajieva, F. M. (2019). DECODING OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH TRANSLATIONS OF THE UZBEK NOVEL "DAYS GONE BY" BY ABDULLA QADIRI (STYLISTIC CORRESPONDENCES AND TRANSFORMATIONS). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 541-545.
14. Khajieva, F. M. (2020). Theoretical aspects of the language learned (Stylistics). *Бухоро: Дурдона*.
15. Хажиева, Ф. (2021). ЛАЙЛА ЛАЛАМИНИНГ "THE MOOR'S ACCOUNT" РОМАНИДА ФОНЕТИК СТИЛИСТИК ВОСИТАЛАР ТАҲЛИЛИ. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 3(8).
16. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2021). The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe. *Central Asian Journal Of Social Sciences And History*, 2(10), 10-14.
17. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). The Problem of "A Strong Personality" in Shakespeare's Dramas: Richard III and Macbeth. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 20, 7-10.

- 18.Zaynitdinovna, T. N. (2022). Lyrical Dialogue in Shakespeare's Poems as a Reflection of Renaissance Anthropocentrism and a Strong Personality. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 21, 120-125.
- 19.Ташева, Н. З. (2022). КРИСТОФЕР МАРЛОУ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ): ТАМЕРЛЕН ВЕЛИКИЙ КАК ТИП ЛИЧНОСТИ ВОСТОЧНОГО ПРАВИТЕЛЯ. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(2), 234-239.
- 20.Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). THE CHARACTER OF STRONG PERSONALITY ACCORDINGLY WITH EASTERN THEMATICS IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S PLAY" TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(08), 9-14.
- 21.Hasanovna, R. S. (2022). IDEAS OF POSTMODERNISM IN THE LITERATURE OF THE XXI CENTURY. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 2(11), 82-87.
- 22.Norova, M. F. (2020). Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (As an example of English and Uzbek languages). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (1), 439-442.
- 23.Norova, M. F. (2020). Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (As an example of English and Uzbek languages). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (1), 439-442.
- 24.Нематова, З. Т., & Хакимова, М. А. (2021). Идеи об идеальном человеке, языке, процветании в эволюции общественно-политических взглядов узбекских джадидов начала XX века. *Central Asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences*, 2(5), 219-224.
- 25.Нематова, З. Т., & Хакимова, М. А. (2020). Songs in teaching English to young second language learners. *Молодой ученый*, (50), 497-499.
- 26.Tursunboevna, N. Z. (2022). Various types of assessment in language teaching and learning. *Eurasian journal of social sciences, philosophy and culture*, 2(3), 140-145.
- 27.Tursunboevna, N. Z., & Asomiddinovich, A. S. (2022). FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING.
- 28.Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(05), 59-65.
- 29.Djalilova, Z. O. (2021). Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 391-397.
- 30.Obidovna, D. Z., & Denis, S. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. *Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences*, 2(6), 5-11.
- 31.Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics. *Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(2), 22-26.
- 32.Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 199-205.
- 33.Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue. *Gender issues*, 7(6).
- 34.JALILOVA, Z. O. (2021, March). ON THE FORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 18-22).
- 35.Jalilova, Z. O. (2020). Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action). *Новый день в медицине*, (4), 501-503.

36.Djalilova, Z. O., Juraev, S. S., & Kosimov, S. M. (2021). LATIN AS A PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL WORKERS. Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА». Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04. 2021., 79.

37.Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. Молодой ученый, (26), 377-379.